

Research Article

Analysis of the Variation in Different Nondestructive Testing and Standards

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A B S T R A C T

Non Destructive Testing (NDT) methods are used to review or measure the materials or designs without annihilating their surface, item uprightness and future handiness. The overall objective of the research is to assess the strength of concrete in existing structures using Nondestructive Tests at Kachankawal Rural Municipality, Jhapa District of Nepal.

Rebound hammer test and ultrasonic pulse velocity tests were used for determining the compressive strength of concrete. The existing Reinforced Concrete Cement culverts were used for 9 existing structures. Average rebound number were taken and calculated from each sample. From the average rebound number were taken to determine the grade of concrete along with corresponding compressive strength. Similarly, the Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity tests were done on same existing structures and path length and time were noted for assessing the corresponding compressive strength and the quality of concrete. Triangulation among rebound hammer test, ultrasonic pulse velocity test and proposed initial grading were validated using chi square test. Relation between compressive strength with rebound hammer and ultrasonic pulse velocity were analyzed using linear regression model.

Chi square confirms variation in compressive strength between calculated compressive strength and standard compressive strength. The relation of compressive strength (y) at $R^2 = 1$ with rebound number (x) and ultrasonic pulse velocity (x) could be expressed as $y = 0.9306x - 2.7233$ and $y = 2.904x + 10.119$ respectively. The study is a guiding tool for concern authority and professionals to make effective decision regarding further structural development and budget allocation of the existing structures.

Keywords: Compressive Strength, Rebound Hammer, Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity, Ingredients of Concrete, Practice of Concreting

Introduction

Concrete is a regularly used composite material in the development business as a result of its solidarity and sturdiness, as well as the accessibility and minimal expense of crude fixings and its capacity to be formed into any ideal engineering shape. Thus, there appear to be an enormous number of existing substantial designs today, and this number is developing constantly. The substantial compressive strength is the most fundamental physical and mechanical quality despite the fact that it is required while fostering a primary part or deciding its heap bearing limit. The compressive strength of cement doesn't actually stay consistent over the long haul because of an assortment of variables, for example, restoring at more youthful ages and inner breaks growing sometime down the road (due to natural or stacking impacts). Whenever there is an uncertainty about nature of cement in another development, the adjustment of the utilization (or capacity) of a construction requires the evaluation of substantial strength to precisely compute the underlying limit, harm brought about by fire, exhaustion, over-burden, or different variables. The necessity for a precise in-situ evaluation of substantial strength in existing constructions is additionally featured by ecological corruption and seismic retrofitting issues that have as of late arisen in a few nations (like Italy and Turkey) (Biondi and Candigliota, 2008; Gunes, 2015).

The initial three occasions plainly relate to new designs, however the last three relate to in-situ assessment of existing constructions. There are an assortment of test strategies for computing in-situ strength. The center test is the most clear strategy for this. Nonetheless, it has various disservices, including being exorbitant, tedious, and at times limited because of troublesome admittance to the center machine. It additionally just addresses a little volume of cement and furthermore has a locally negative impact simply on building (Meynink and Samarin, 1979).

Nondestructive testing strategies, for example, bounce back hammer, ultrasonic heartbeat speed, test infiltration, pullout, and sever are frequently used to decide in-situ substantial strength. These methods are recognized by their straightforwardness, speed, and low cost (instead of a center test). Their primary inconvenience is that they are aberrant methodologies since they can't quantify precisely in-situ strength. They take estimations of different boundaries, and strength is determined utilizing a "change model" that relates the solidarity to the deliberate characteristics. Since concrete is such a different material, there is no single model that applies to all cements (Breyse, 2012).

As a result, our present technique depends on both horrendous and nondestructive examinations to construct a transformation model for each situation. The determined model is then used to assess substantial strength at test

places where nondestructive estimation values for the substantial viable are accessible.

After the substantial has solidified, it is as often as possible expected to look at the development to check whether it is adequate for its planned use. Such test ought to in a perfect world be done without making any harm the substantial (Jedidi and Machta, 2014) The tests utilized for substantial testing range from totally non-horrendous tests, which make no harm the substantial, to somewhat disastrous tests, for example, center testing and pull-out and pull-off tests, which require the surface to be supplanted or fixed once the test is finished. This review will make sense of and stress the need of taking on nondestructive strategies, for example, the Rebound Hammer and ultrasonic heartbeat speed test, which are both simple to perform and frequently savvy (Jedidi and Machta, 2014). One of the upsides of UPV is its capacity to be utilized in research facilities as well as at explicit spots.

This study's relevance can be described as follows:

- Technique for recommendations for improving the dependability of non-destructive testing for assessing strength in existing concrete structures
- Provides information about the condition of existing concrete structures and their strength
- Provides knowledge regarding methods of NDT and procedures to be used for obtaining the required concrete strength
- Provides knowledge regarding the budget planning such a way that work is completed in time without delays in construction

Research Objectives

The overall objective of the research is to analyze the variation in compressive strengths of rebound hammer test, ultrasonic pulse velocity test and standards of existing structures at Kachankawal Rural Municipality, Jhapa District of Nepal.

Following are the specific objectives to support the overall objectives

- To analyze the compressive strength of concrete using Non Destructive Tests of existing structures at Kachankawal Rural Municipality
- To analyze the variation in compressive strengths of rebound hammer test, ultrasonic pulse velocity test and standards

Theoretical Review

Non-destructive tests, such as the rebound hammer test and ultrasonic pulse velocity test, are utilized to assess existing designs or when the substantial's quality is being referred to. The two strategies highlight an elevated degree of substantial

quality at work (Mohamad R. Abdulkadir et.al, 2017). Non-destructive and partly destructive tests can look at a wide scope of boundaries, including essential determinations like densities, flexible modules, and qualities, as well as surface hardness, layer retention, support area, size, and surface distance. Squashing examples is the standard damaging test for deciding substantial strength (Akhilchandran and JibinBabu, 2015). Non-destructive techniques, such as rebound hammer testing and ultrasonic testing meaningfully affect structures and need the protection of designs and biological systems. Non-destructive techniques tests are regularly used to survey the mechanical characteristics and solidness of substantial structures.

The aftereffects of a few Non-destructive techniques test methods can be utilized to survey the strength of cement anytime in a current primary part. The connection between's the consequences of various non-damaging strategies and the compressive strength of cement acquired by testing substantial center examples or substantial solid shape tests can be utilized to make a recipe for deciding genuine substantial strength. The motivation behind this work is to utilize the discoveries of the bounce back hammer test and the ultrasonic heartbeat speed test to decide the substantial strength of existing designs

Rebound Hammer

The rebound numbers are determined by a variety of factors, including the type of cement and aggregate used, the surface condition and moisture content of the concrete, the age of the concrete, and the degree of carbonation. As a result, the estimation of concrete strength using rebound hammer method cannot be held to be particularly precise, and the likely accuracy of concrete strength prediction in a structure is ± 25 percent.

very good quality concrete has an average rebound number greater than 40, good quality concrete has an average rebound number between 30-40, fair quality concrete has an average rebound number between 20-30, poor quality concrete has an average rebound number less than 20, and delaminated concrete has an average rebound number less than 20.

Procedure

To achieve reliable findings, the rebound hammer must be tested against the testing anvil before beginning the test. Steel with a Brinell hardness of about 5000 N/mm² should be used as the testing anvil. The rebound hammer's supplier/ manufacturer should specify the range of anvil readings that are appropriate for different types of rebound hammers.

The best way to establish a link between concrete's compressive strength and its rebound number is to measure both qualities on concrete cubes at the same time. The

concrete cube specimens are placed in a compression testing machine under a constant load, the rebound number is measured, and the compressive strength is calculated according to IS: 516- 1959. At the point when the sledge's effect energy is around 2.2 Nm, the proper burden required is on the request for 7 N/mm². While aligning bounce back hammers with higher effect energy, the heap ought to be expanded, and while adjusting bounce back hammers with lower sway energy, the heap ought to be dropped. To limit the size impact on the test aftereffect of a full scale development, the test examples ought to be pretty much as extensive as could really be expected. For aligning bounce back hammers with lower sway energy (2.2 Nm), 150 mm 3D square examples are great, but test solid shapes with higher effect energy, like 30 Nm, ought not be more modest than 300 mm.

Assuming the examples have been wet relieved, they ought to be taken from the wet stockpiling and put away in the research facility climate for no less than 24 hours prior to testing. It is vital to lay out a connection between's the strength of wet tried 3D squares and the strength of dry tried solid shapes on which bounce back readings are taken to get a relationship between's bounce back numbers and strength of wet relieved and wet tried blocks. It isn't fitting to make an immediate relationship between the bounce back numbers on wet shapes and the strength of wet blocks. Just the block's upward faces as cast ought to be tried. While utilizing the bounce back hammers, no less than nine readings ought to be taken on every one of the two vertical countenances accessible in the pressure testing hardware. The puts of effect on the example should not be nearer than 20 mm to an edge and should be somewhere around 20 mm separated. Similar focuses ought not be affected two times.

For testing, smooth, clean and dry surface is to be selected. If loosely adhering scale is present, this should be rubbed off with a grinding wheel or stone. Rough surfaces resulting from incomplete compaction, loss of grout, spalled or tooled surfaces do not give reliable results and should be avoided.

The point of impact should be at least 20 mm away from any edge or shape discontinuity.

For taking a measurement, the rebound hammer should be held at right angles to the surface of the concrete member. The test can thus be conducted horizontally on vertical surfaces or vertically upwards or downwards on horizontal surfaces. If the situation demands, the rebound hammer can be held at intermediate angles also, but in each case, the rebound number will be different for the same concrete.

Rebound hammer test is directed around every one of the marks of perception on all available appearances of the primary component. Substantial surfaces are totally

cleaned prior to taking any estimation. Around each mark of perception, six readings of bounce back files are taken and normal of these readings subsequent to erasing anomalies according to IS: 8900-1978 turns into the bounce back record for the place of perception.

Impact of Test Conditions

The bounce back numbers are affected by various variables like kinds of concrete and total, surface condition and dampness content, time of cement and degree of carbonation of concrete..

- Impact of Type of Cement
- Impact of Type of Aggregate
- Impact of Surface Condition and Moisture Content of Concrete
- Impact of Curing and Age of Concrete
- Impact of Carbonation of Concrete Surface

Ultra Sonic Pulse Velocity

The essential idea for determining concrete quality is that when the density, homogeneity, and consistency of the concrete are good, higher velocities can be achieved. Lower velocities are obtained when the quality is poor. If there is a crack, void, or fault in the concrete that prevents the pulses from being transmitted, the pulse power is reduced and the pulses pass around the discontinuity, lengthening the path. As a result, lower velocities are achieved. The exact pulse velocity obtained is mostly determined by the concrete components and mix quantities. The pulse velocity is also influenced by the aggregate density and modulus of elasticity.

A wave propagation test is what UPV testing is. It emits electro acoustic pulses from one side through the concrete medium, receives the signal from the other side, and measures the transit time. The transmitting and receiving points' path lengths are measured, and the pulse velocity is determined by dividing the path length by the transit time.

The characteristics of concrete, which define its elastic stiffness and mechanical strength, influence pulse velocity. If the concrete under test has low compaction, voids, or damaged material, the pulse velocity will be reduced. As the concrete ages, deteriorates, or changes over time, the pulse velocity increases or decreases. This technology is regarded as a valuable and trustworthy non-destructive means of inspecting the interior of concrete.

Procedure

The transducer, which is retained in contact with one surface of the concrete member under test, generates the ultrasonic pulse in this test procedure. The pulse of vibrations is transformed into an electrical signal by the second transducer retained in touch with the other surface of the concrete part after travelling a specified route length

L in the concrete, and the transit time (T) of the pulse can be measured using an electronic timing circuit. The pulse velocity (V) is calculated as follows:

$$V = L/T$$

The most energy is proliferated at right points to the essence of the communicating transducer after the ultrasonic heartbeat encroaches on the material's surface, consequently the best outcomes are gotten while the getting transducer is put on the contrary substance of the substantial part (direct transmission or cross examining). Be that as it may, as a rule, the primary part's two went against countenances may not be available for estimations. The getting transducer is likewise situated on similar face of the substantial individuals in such conditions (surface examining). Surface examining is less effective than cross examining on the grounds that the sign created at the getting transducer is simply 2 to 3% of that delivered by cross testing, and the experimental outcomes are affected incredibly by the surface layers of cement, which might have unexpected properties in comparison to the substantial inside the primary part. On a similar substantial component, the roundabout speed is generally more modest than the immediate speed. This error could go from 5% to 20%, contingent upon the nature of the substantial being tried. By and large, a distinction of generally 0.5 km/sec can be found in passing mark concrete.

It is basic to have fitting acoustical coupling between the substantial and the essence of every transducer for the ultrasonic heartbeats created at the sending transducer to go into the substantial and be identified by the getting transducer. Petrol jam, oil, fluid cleanser, and kaolin glycerol glue are normal couplets. Assuming that the substantial surface is very harsh, it is important to smooth and even out a region of the surface where the transducer will be introduced. It is desirable over screen beat speed over a more drawn out way length than would commonly be used while chipping away at substantial surfaces created by ordinary cycles, for example, trowelling. For the immediate transmission strategy including one unmoulded surface, a base way length of 150 mm is encouraged, and for the surface testing approach including one unmoulded surface, a base way length of 400 mm is suggested.

Transducer regular frequencies ought to in a perfect world be in the scope of 20 to 150 kHz. For short way lengths, high recurrence transducers are liked, and for long way lengths, low recurrence transducers are liked. Most all-around applications benefit from transducers with a recurrence of 50 to 60 kHz.

Since total size influences beat speed estimation, it is suggested that the base course length for concrete with an ostensible greatest total size of 20 mm or less be 100 mm,

and 150 mm for concrete with a notional most extreme total size of 20 to 40 mm be 150 mm.

Given the innate unusualness of test discoveries, an adequate number of readings are taken by separating the whole design into suitable lattice markings of 30 x 30 cm or much more modest. Every network crossing point turns into a site of perception.

To quantify the ultrasonic heartbeat speed by direct transmission, for example cross examining, transducers are put on relating puts of perception on restricting countenances of a primary part. Surface examining is utilized to survey ultrasonic heartbeat speed on one face of the underlying part in the event that one of the countenances isn't open.

Surface probing generally results in a lower pulse velocity than cross probing, with a difference of up to 1 km/sec depending on the number of parameters.

The Direct Transmission setup is thought of as the most dependable.

UPV transducers should be in finished contact with the substantial surface; if not, a blunder will happen because of an air pocket between the transducer and the substantial. To lay out appropriate contact between the UPV transducer and the surface, mixtures, for example, petrol jam, oil, fluid cleanser, and kaolin-glycerol glue can be used.

Translation of Result

Concrete's ultrasonic heartbeat speed still up in the air by its thickness and modulus of versatility. This, thus, is reliant upon the materials and blend extents utilized in substantial creation, as well as the way of substantial situation, compaction, and relieving. For instance, on the off chance that the substantial isn't compacted as completely as could be expected, or then again assuming there is isolation of cement during setting or there are inward breaks or imperfections, the beat speed will be lower, albeit similar materials and blend extents are utilized.

The consistency, occurrence or nonappearance of inside blemishes, breaks and isolation, and different attributes of substantial that are characteristic of the degree of workmanship utilized can be evaluated involving the rules in Table 2, which have been produced for describing the nature of cement in structures with regards to ultrasonic heartbeat speed.

Since genuine upsides of the beat speed got, rely upon various boundaries, any model for surveying the nature of cement based on beat speed as given in Table 2 can be held as agreeable just to an overall degree. In any case, when the correlation is made among various pieces of a design, which have been worked simultaneously with probably comparative materials, development practices

and management, the evaluation of value turns out to be more significant and dependable.

The estimation of cement compressive strength utilizing ultrasonic heartbeat speed values is lacking since the connection between's ultrasonic heartbeat speed and cement compressive strength has a low factual certainty. The justification for this is that there are a few factors having an effect on everything, every one of which distinctively affects the beat speed and compressive strength of cement. Assuming that genuine substantial materials and blend extents utilized in a design are accessible, a substantial strength gauge can be made by laying out an appropriate connection between's the beat speed and the compressive strength of substantial examples made with such materials and blend extents, under ecological circumstances like those in the construction. The projected strength might vary by 20% from the genuine strength. The subsequent connection may not be pertinent to cement of an alternate grade or made with different materials.

Table 1. Velocity Criteria for Concrete Quality Grading

Velocity (km/sec)	Concrete Quality
>4.0	Very good to excellent
3.5-4.0	Good to very good slight prosperity may exists
3.0-3.5	Satisfactory but loss of integrity is suspected
<3.0	Poor and loss of integrity exists

The quality of concrete can be predicted after the calculation of velocity, the test having velocity greater than 4 km/s is considered as concrete with excellent quality, similarly concrete with velocity value between 3.5 to 4 as good quality, 3 to 3.5 as satisfactory and below 3 as poor quality.

Study Area

This is a nondestructive testing study aimed at evaluating the structural strength of buildings in Nepal's Kachankawal Rural Municipality. During construction, a large number of old structures break or collapse. Many buildings are left unfinished due to a lack of adequate funding, and then they are completed without thorough testing. This research aids in determining the structural integrity of existing structures in the Kachankawal Rural Municipality. Facts of Kachankawal Rural Municipality

Official Name:	Kachankawal Rural Municipality
Location:	26.4257° N, 87.9666° E
Altitude range:	49m-70m from sea level.
Temperature:	10°C to 40°C.
Area:	11000 Hector.
No. of wards:	7

Total structures constructed: 80 no (in F/Y 2076-77)

Research Flowchart

The flowchart of research activities is shown in Figure 1. In this study, a diagnostic and descriptive research approach will be used. The research process begins with NDT and evaluation indicators/ measurements, then moves on to data analysis, evaluation and decision making, acceptance or rejection, and finally report authoring.

Figure 1. Flow chart of research process

Sampling

Most of the Structures are designed following Nepal National Building Code and DUBBC Standards. The total population of Kachankawal Rural Municipality is 40000 in 7 wards.

All of the countries have code and guidelines for safety construction. However, this codes and guidelines does not seem working due to various reasons at construction sites. Most of the workers are untrained and unaware of guidelines. Hence, the quality of the works also cannot be assured (Aryal and Mishra,2020).

In this investigation, the non-destructive test is used. Because this test uses two separate NDT methods, rebound hammer tests and Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity test, the number of samples will be limited to 21 due to time and resources. A total of 9 structures will be chosen in a randomized manner from various wards to represent the entire area. Three sample sites will be chosen at random from each structure.

Data Collection

For this research following data were collected.

Primary Data

Primary data for the research study is collected at sites. Primary data consists:

- The Existing structures (RCC culverts and buildings) site. The Data area taken from either Column or Slab.
- Proportion of ingredients for used for making concrete collected at site.
- Checklist & Observation about perception & practice of people towards concreting.

Sample Collection

Rebound Hammar

The average rebound number was determined from several locations of existing structures at a gap of 25 cm each, using three data points from each existing structure aimed at varied mean strengths.

Testing of Specimen

The inspector then gently moves the instrument toward the test surface until the hammer impacts after the gadget has been lined up and the angle has been recorded. Maintain pressure on the instrument after impact and depress the side button to lock the plunger in the retracted position. After that, the rebound number is rounded up to the next whole number.

Nine readings were taken from each test location to assure accuracy. Furthermore, the spacing between impact locations was maintained at 25 mm, and the distance between impact points and the member’s edges was maintained at 50 mm. When an impact smashes or breaks through a near-surface air void, the reading should be ignored and a new one recorded.

The rebound number for the same concrete was discovered to be variable due to varying effects of gravity on the rebound as the test angle was adjusted.

The Rebound numbers (rebound index), Mean Rebound Value at the time of testing, Breaking Load, Predicted Compressive Strength as predicted by the Rebound Hammer, and Actual Compressive Strength as achieved by the Compression Testing Machine are listed in the tables below.

Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity Tester

To ensure the accuracy of the measurement and operation of the equipment, the equipment should be calibrated before beginning the observation and again at the end of the test. It’s done by using a standard calibration rod that comes with the instrument to measure transit time. To gain access to the measuring areas, a suitable platform/

staging should be created. Prior to taking the measurement, the spot should be marked and numbered with chalk or something similar (pre decided locations).

Map Showing Sample Collection Locations

Figure 2. Map Showing Sample Collection Locations

Secondary Data Collection

Secondary data regarding to study was collected from various sources.

- DOR and NBC of Nepal: Data for Minimum compressive strength required for concrete for buildings designed as per Norms of NBC and DOR of Nepal
- Kachankawal R. Municipality: Existing Structures data, population data

Data Base Preparation

All recorded and observed data was entered in MS-Excel for further analysis.

Test of Validity of Data

By repeating the experiment, the correctness of the instrument's findings for assessing compressive strength was confirmed.

The data was associated and compared with a set of other data brought from the lab to determine the veracity of the measured data. The data in this study correlated with these other ideas or facts in a predictable way. As a result, we came to the conclusion that the information received was accurate.

Analysis of Data

Visual Inspection

The first step in evaluating a concrete structure is to examine the condition of the concrete, noting any defects, the presence of cracking and the type of cracking (crack width, depth, spacing, density), the presence of rust marks on

the surface, the presence of voids, and the presence of seemingly poorly compacted areas, among other things. Visual evaluation determines whether or not a detailed study should be pursued.

The Rebound Hammer Test

The Schmidt rebound hammer is essentially a surface hardness test, with no obvious theoretical relationship between concrete strength and the hammer's rebound number. Surface hardness of concrete can't be immediately transferred to compressive strength, hence rebound hammers are used to measure it. The method essentially assesses the near-surface concrete's modulus of elasticity. The principle is based on the absorption of a portion of the spring's stored elastic energy through plastic deformation of the rock surface and the propagation of ten mechanical waves through the stone, while the remaining elastic energy causes the hammer to rebound. The Rebound number is the distance traveled by the mass, represented as a percentage of the spring's initial extension. Because of the heterogeneous nature of near-surface features, there is a lot of variation in rebound numbers (principally due to near-surface aggregate particles). Surface smoothness and finish, moisture level, coarse aggregate type, and the presence of carbonation are all factors that influence rebound hammer test results in addition to concrete strength. Although rebound hammers can be used to assess concrete strength, the rebound values must be compared to the compressive strength of molded specimens or structure cores.

Determination of Pulse Velocity

An electro acoustical transducer in contact with one surface of the concrete member under test generates a longitudinal vibration pulse. The pulse of vibration is transformed into an electrical signal by a second electro-acoustical transducer after crossing a specified path length (L) in the concrete, allowing the transit time (T) of the pulse to be measured.

The pulse velocity (V) is given by $V = L / T$ where, V = Pulse velocity, L = Path length, T = Time taken by the pulse to traverse the path length.

Compressive Strength of Concrete

We set up our hypotheses against a suitable strength in one sample test for a discrete result. On the sample data, we select a sample and compute descriptive statistics. We calculate the sample size (n) as well as the proportions of participants in each response type. $(\hat{p}_1, \hat{p}_2, \dots, \hat{p}_k)$ where k represents the number of response categories. The proper test statistic for the hypothesis test is then determined. The test statistic's formula is shown below.

Test Statistic for Testing $H_0: p_1 = p_{10}, p_2 = p_{20}, \dots, p_k = p_{k0}$

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E} \quad (\text{Chaudhary and Mishra, 2022}).$$

The critical value for the chi-square distribution with degrees of freedom (df) = k-1 is found in a table of probability. In each of the response categories, O = observed frequency and E = expected frequency are used in the test statistic. The observed frequencies are those found in the sample, while the predicted frequencies are calculated as follows. Another probability distribution that ranges from 0 to is the 2 (chi-square). For large samples, defined as predicted frequencies of at least 5 in each of the response categories, the test above statistic formula is adequate.

A 2 test compares observed frequencies in each response category to expected frequencies if the null hypothesis were true. These predicted frequencies are calculated by allocating the sample to the response categories based on the H0 distribution. This is done by multiplying the observed sample size (n) by the null hypothesis proportions (p 10 , p 20 , ..., p k0). We need to make sure that min (np10, n p20,..., n pk0) > 5 to verify that the sample size is appropriate for using the test statistic above.

The 2 goodness-of-fit tests is a hypothesis test with a discrete result evaluated in a single sample, with the purpose of

determining whether the distribution of responses follows a known distribution. The goal, as the name implies, is to see if the pattern or distribution of answers in the sample "fits" a given concrete strength.

Findings & Discussion

Schmidt Hammer (Rebound Hammer Test)

When the plunger of a rebound hammer is forced on the concrete's surface, the spring controls mass rebounds, the extent of which is determined by the concrete's surface hardness. The compressive strength of the concrete is thought to be connected to the surface hardness and thus the rebound. The rebound number or rebound index is calculated by reading the rebound along a graduated scale.

The rebound numbers are determined by a variety of factors, including the type of cement and aggregate used, the surface condition and moisture content of the concrete, the age of the concrete, and the degree of carbonation. As a result, the assessment of concrete strength using the rebound hammer method cannot be considered highly precise, and the likely accuracy of concrete strength prediction in a structure is +/-25percent.

Table 3.Schmidt Hammer test results

S. No.	Structural Element	Location	Average Rebound Number	Quality of Concrete	Remarks
1.	Culvert 1	Kachankawal-1	32.56	Good	30-40
2.	Culvert 2	Kachankawal-2	31.33	Good	30-40
3.	Culvert 3	Kachankawal-3	28.50	Fair	20-30
4.	Culvert 4	Kachankawal-4	28.50	Fair	20-30
5.	Culvert 5	Kachankawal-5	26.32	Fair	20-30
6.	Culvert 6	Kachankawal-5	25.90	Fair	20-30
7.	Culvert 7	Kachankawal-6	24.50	Fair	20-30
8.	Culvert 8	Kachankawal-7	23.90	Fair	20-30
9.	Culvert 9	Kachankawal-7	22.20	Fair	20-30

Table 4.Ultrasonic pulse velocity test results

S. No.	Test Element/ Location	Path Length (mm)	Transmit Time in micro sec	Pulse velocity (km/s)	Standard Value	Concrete Quality	Remarks
1.	Culvert 1	400	98.00	4.48	>4	V.Good	
2.	Culvert 2	400	96.50	4.23	>4	V.Good	
3.	Culvert 3	400	94.50	4.23	>4	V.Good	
4.	Culvert 4	400	98.60	4.06	>4	V.Good	
5.	Culvert 5	400	105.60	3.79	3.5 to 4.0	Good	
6.	Culvert 6	400	106.20	3.69	3.5 to 4.0	Good	
7.	Culvert 7	400	113.60	3.38	3.0 to 3.5	Satisfactory	
8.	Culvert 8	400	116.50	3.29	3.0 to 3.5	Satisfactory	
9.	Culvert 9	400	115.10	3.33	3.0 to 3.5	Satisfactory	

As shown in table 3, culvert 1 and 2 are found to have good quality of concrete with range between 30-40, other culvert 3 to 9 were found to have fair quality ranging between 20-30. The Schmidt Hammer Test were done on different Culverts; it was done for the compressive strength test of the structural component for approved drawing.

It was done under the supervision of the Rural Municipal Technical Teams and was found that it was in design value verifying the quality Management Practice of Kachankawal Rural Municipality is within the satisfactory Level.

Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity Tester

A non-destructive Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity (UPV) test is used to assess the quality of concrete and natural rocks. The velocity of an ultrasonic pulse flowing through a concrete construction or natural rock formation is measured in this test to determine the strength and quality of concrete or rock.

This test is carried out by sending an ultrasonic pulse into the concrete being tested and measuring the time it takes for the pulse to pass through the construction. Slower velocities may suggest concrete with many fractures or voids, whereas higher velocities indicate good quality and continuity of the material.

The Ultra Sonic Pulse velocity test was conducted for assessing the quality of concrete leading to the test of the Quality performance practice of Kachankawal Rural

Municipality. The comparatively higher velocities are obtained when the quality of the concrete in terms of density, homogeneity crack, void or flaw inside the concrete is in compact condition which comes in the way of transmission of pulses, the pulses strength is attenuated and it passed around the discontinuity, thereby making the path length longer. Consequently, Lower velocities are obtained. The pulse velocity found ranges from 3.29 km/s to 4.48 km/s shows medium to Good condition of the Structural component.

From table 4, culvert 1 to 4 the pulse velocity was found between 4.06 to 4.48 with standard value >4 with very good concrete quality, culvert 5 and 6 were found ranging from 3.5 to 4 with good quality of concrete, culvert 7,8 and 9 were found ranging from 3 to 3.5 with satisfactory concrete quality.

Hence, as per the test result (velocity reading) clearly indicate the quality of concrete is being acceptable condition.

Comparison of compressive strength obtained from rebound hammer using Chi-square test

Summary for X^2 Test:

The observed rebound hammer number is used for calculation of compressive strength of sampled concrete structures using formula $0.9306 \cdot RH - 2.7233$ given by Katuwal 2019.

Table 5: Rebound Hammer test data calculations

S.No.	Sample	Observed Compressive Strength Value	Expected Standard Compressive Strength	$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$
		(O)	(E)	
1.	C1	27.58	20	2.87
2.	C2	26.43	20	2.07
3.	C3	23.80	20	0.72
4.	C4	23.80	20	0.72
5.	C5	21.77	20	0.16
6.	C6	21.38	20	0.10
7.	C7	20.08	20	0.00
8.	C8	19.52	20	0.01
9.	C9	17.94	20	0.21
		Total	$\chi^2=$	6.86

For,

Level of Significance = 5%,

Degree of Freedom = $N-1 = 8$,

Critical Value = **6.86**

Decision: Since, $\chi^2 = 6.86 < 15.51$ (Critical Value). Thus Null Hypothesis H_0 is accepted. Hence there is significant difference between the calculated compressive strength and standard compressive strength. Thus, calculated compressive strength varies with standard value due to various factors (age, weather, temperature, methods of concreting etc.).

Relation between Rebound Number and Compressive Strength

Figure 3. Relation between rebound number and compressive strength of concrete

As shown in a Figure 3, a scatter diagram is plotted between rebound number and compressive strength where obtained rebound number is kept at x axis and compressive strength is kept in y axis.

$$Y = 0.30X - 2.723 \tag{1}$$

Where Y is compressive strength and x is obtained rebound number.

compressive strength of sampled concrete structures using formula $CS = 2.904V + 10.119$ given by: Ofuyatan et al. 2021.

As shown in a figure 5, a scatter line diagram is plotted between ultrasonic pulse velocity and compressive strength where calculated upv is kept at x axis and compressive strength is kept in y axis.

$$Y = 2.904X + 10.11 \tag{2}$$

Where Y is compressive strength and x is calculated ultrasonic pulse velocity.

Conclusion

- Almost 90% of the Existing Structures sampled in Kachankawal Rural Municipality complies with the minimum compressive strength of concrete as required by NBC and as per norms of DOR of Nepal.
- Out of 9 selected samples 2 good and 7 fair were found based on rebound hammer test whereas, 4, 2 and 3 samples were very good, good and satisfactory respectively based on ultrasonic pulse velocity test.
- Chi square confirms variation in compressive strength between calculated compressive strength and standard compressive strength.
- The relation of compressive strength(y) at $R^2 = 1$ with

Table 6. Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity test data calculations

S.No.	Sample	Observed Compressive Strength Value	Expected Standard Compressive Strength	$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
		(O)	(E)	
1.	C1	21.97	20	0.49
2.	C2	22.16	20	0.29
3.	C3	22.41	20	0.29
4.	C4	21.90	20	0.18
5.	C5	21.14	20	0.06
6.	C6	20.83	20	0.03
7.	C7	19.94	20	0.00
8.	C8	19.67	20	0.01
9.	C9	19.77	20	0.00
		Total	$\chi^2 =$	1.01

For,

Level of Significance = 5%,

Degree of Freedom = N-1 = 8,

Critical Value = 1.01

Decision: Since, $\chi^2 = 1.01 < 15.51$ (Critical Value). Thus Null Hypothesis H_0 is accepted. Hence there is significant difference between the calculated compressive strength and standard compressive strength. Thus, calculated compressive strength varies with standard value due to various factors (age, weather, temperature, methods of concreting etc.)

Comparison of Compressive Strength Obtained from Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity using Chi-square Test

The obtained pulse velocity is used for calculation of

rebound number(x) and ultrasonic pulse velocity(x) could be expressed as $y = 0.9306x - 2.7233$ and $y = 2.904x + 10.119$ respectively.

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